

Working for the environment: Farmer attitudes towards sustainable farming actions in rural Wales, UK*Elizabeth Follett,¹ Lorna Davis,² Catherine Wilson,³ Jo Cable⁴*¹Department of Civil Engineering and Industrial Design, School of Engineering, University of Liverpool, Liverpool, UK²Sudsplanter Ltd., Bradford on Avon, Wiltshire, UK³Hydro-environmental Research Centre, School of Engineering, Cardiff University, Cardiff, Wales, UK⁴School of Biosciences, Cardiff University, Cardiff, Wales, UK**Abstract**

Recognition of land management impacts on water quality and flooding, and climate change induced increases in storm intensity and flood risk, have led to interest in farmer provision of ecosystem services alongside food production. However, pathways for practical design and funding of agroecological interventions are less well understood. Effective design and implementation of sustainable farming initiatives has been linked to human-centred aspects including stakeholder engagement and the provision of social and economic co-benefits. To deepen understanding of user approaches and perspectives, Welsh farmer perspectives on sustainable farming were obtained through discussion, online polls, and questionnaires. Participant-identified barriers to action included incorporation of return on initial time and cost investment in long-term farm budgets, occurrence of extreme weather events, and tenanted land. Decision-making processes were rooted in community discussion to balance perceived needs of the land and farm business, with communication preferences expressed for bilingual farm advice provision and support of farmer-to-farmer knowledge transfer pathways. Participants identified interdependent components of economic, social, cultural, and environmental sustainability necessary to achieve positive environmental outcomes, resembling Bourdieu social theory. Design of tree planting schemes was discussed as an example of this interlinkage, with positive attitudes expressed for land sharing at small spatial scales, but not at the whole-farm scale.

Keywords: sustainable farming; environmental land management; Wales; public goods; land sparing.

Abbreviations: NFU/National Farmers' Union

1. Introduction

Farmers play a crucial role in sustaining ecosystem services of clean water, air and habitat provision, as well as food production (O'Connell et al. 2007; Hewett et al. 2019). Farmers manage 85% of Wales' land area (Wiseall 2016), maintaining and enhancing the natural environment for aesthetic enjoyment and wellbeing of the wider population. Their provision of ecosystem services ranges from habitat creation and management of water storage to reducing flood impacts and carbon capture (O'Connell et al. 2007; Hewett et al. 2019). The benefits of agroecological schemes aiming to increase provision of ecosystem services have gained particular relevance as climate change is expected to increase summer storm intensity and temperature, increase sediment runoff and decrease water quality (IPCC 2014; NERC 2016). In addition, intensification of UK agriculture following the Second World War has increased soil compaction, runoff from bare soil, and river channelisation, increasing the potential for sediment loss and decreased downstream water quality (Boardman et al. 2003; O'Connell et al. 2007). The importance of farming practices in protecting ecosystem services, including downstream water quality (Carroll et al. 2006; Belmont et al. 2011; Schottler et al. 2013; McIntyre et al. 2014), has led to widespread international interest in recognizing and rewarding agricultural land management actions expected to lead to positive environmental outcomes (Burton et al. 2008, NFU Cymru 2018, Welsh Government 2019a; OECD 2020; Reilly and Mercier 2021; Cusworth and Dodsworth 2021). Internationally (Kummer 2021; Graddy-Lovelace 2020) and in Wales (Hyland et al. 2016; Case 2021), farmers have called for technical advice and funding to aid adaptation to climate change-induced stressors and provide compensation for practices that increase provision of ecosystem services.

While the role of farmers in ecosystem service provision has been recognized, pathways for practical design and funding of interventions are less well understood. Recognition of the complex social, economic, and political aspects related to farming practice (Burnett 2023) has led to calls for

development of “people-centred nature-based solutions” that support local social, economic and political needs (Fleischman et al. 2020). The concept of “people-centred nature-based solutions” echoes broader international standards for “human-centred design” targeting interactive systems. The International Standards Organisation requires that human-centred approaches base design on six principles including an explicit understanding of users, tasks, and environments, incorporation of users throughout design and development, that design is driven and refined by user-centred evaluation, that the process is iterative, the design addresses the whole user experience, and that the design team includes multidisciplinary skills and perspectives (ISO, 2019). Stakeholder involvement in codesign harnesses available expertise in optimal placement and design of interventions to maximise benefit to the farm business (Cudsworth and Dodsworth 2021). Further, focus on the inner drivers for farmers’ choices and perspectives towards agroecological schemes has been advocated to enable sustained, transformational changes based on investigation of farmer pathways to change in the Netherlands (Bakker et al. 2023). More broadly, successful implementation of nature-based solutions for natural flood management has been linked to human-centred aspects including stakeholder engagement and the provision of social and economic co-benefits. A catchment-wide approach including stakeholder involvement in knowledge co-production, co-creation, and intervention design has been advocated for successful implementation of catchment systems engineering (Hewett et al. 2020).

Additional challenges for intervention design and implementation raised by farming in resource-poor regions has been highlighted historically (Pretty 1991) and in contemporary examination of agroecological schemes (Fraser et al. 2014). In Wales, land use is dominated by grassland pasture due to high prevalence of upland, mountainous regions and wet climate, with 61% of Welsh farmland classed as a Less Favourable Area (LFA) for agriculture (Figure 1). Examination of conversion from conventional to organic farming methods within LFAs in England and Wales (Fraser et al. 2014) observed that limited increases in habitat diversity were linked to constrained management options due to physical conditions of the LFA, leading to calls for additional evidence related to farming and agroecological management in such regions.

To inform effective design and implementation of sustainable farming actions by deepening understanding of user approaches and perspectives, and to aid development of agroecological policy, Welsh farmer perspectives on sustainable farming actions were investigated through an engagement project centred on four research questions: What are the main barriers to implementation of sustainable farming actions by Welsh farmers? What is the decision-making process of Welsh farmers towards sustainable farming actions? How should information on sustainable farming be communicated to Welsh farmers? What suggestions do farmers have for the future of sustainable farming in Wales? In addition to directly addressing project research questions, participants built on the term “sustainable farming” to highlight broader interlinkage between environmental sustainability and social, economic, and cultural aspects of sustainability.

2. Methods

Project activities targeted Welsh farmers. In Wales, land use is dominated by grassland pasture due to high prevalence of upland, mountainous regions and wet climate, with 61% of Welsh farmland classed as a Less Favourable Area for agriculture (Figure 1). Challenges for intervention design and implementation raised by farming in such regions has been highlighted during examination of conversion from conventional to organic farming methods within Less Favourable Areas (LFA) in England and Wales (Fraser et al. 2014). Observations of limited increases in habitat diversity were linked to constrained management options due to physical conditions of the LFA, highlighting a need for additional evidence related to farming and biodiversity in such regions. Previous research examined identity and attitudes of English farmers participating in the Environmental Land Management scheme (Cusworth and Dodsworth 2021), contributing to development of successful incentive-based schemes for England. However, a similar widespread agri-environment scheme does not currently exist in Wales.

Project delivery targeted three counties across Wales (Monmouthshire, Pembrokeshire, and Anglesey; Figure 1). Pembrokeshire contained a higher prevalence of arable cropland (Welsh Government 2017),

and Anglesey and Pembrokeshire a higher percentage of Welsh speakers (67%, 32%; Monmouthshire 18.8%; Welsh Government Office for National Statistics 2022). A project summary was provided to farmers' union county representatives along with a supporting e-mail in Welsh and English. Representatives advertised workshops via email and orally at county meetings. Phone calls were made to at least 25 farmers per county known to have an interest in sustainable farming. To reach a broad audience of potential participants (6,000 member farmers) and provide a transparent overview of project goals to the community, a project outline was published in the NFU Cymru magazine (July 2021).

Figure 1. (A) Map of survey areas in Wales, UK: Isle of Anglesey, Monmouthshire, and Pembrokeshire counties indicated by solid black arrows. County boundaries (grey solid lines, UK Office of National Statistics 2018). Border with England denoted with solid dark grey line. (B) Classification of agricultural land (Welsh Government 2019b).

Online workshops (July 2021) and in-person visits (August, September 2021) presented information on sustainable farming actions with discussion around project research questions, supported by online polls or paper questionnaires depending on meeting setting. Content focused on water quality measurement methods and sustainable farming actions applicable to grazed and arable land, including buffer strips, sediment traps, sediment barriers, vegetated ditches and swales, and preventing surface runoff from yard areas. An initial set of three meetings targeted individual counties (July 2021; 4, 3, and 3 participants). Anonymised transcripts of discussion were collated during the meeting, and anonymous poll responses were visible to participants and downloaded. In-person meetings were hosted on participant farms in Pembrokeshire (August 2021; 9 participants) and Anglesey (September 2021; 11 participants), with anonymous paper questionnaires replacing online polls. On-farm walkover visits were offered to all participants, with two participants accepting. Short information sheets were presented at the Pembrokeshire Fair (20 visitors, August 2021). Following in-person meetings, an interview was conducted with the project member leading the visit, recorded via written summary (September 2021). A summary online workshop held for all counties (November 2021; 5 participants) described methods used for qualitative data analysis and presented initial results including a summary of Table 1, draft Figure 3, illustrated infographic, and technical drawings for a related art piece to participants for verification and revision.

2.1 Method limitations

We recognise that the low sample size and voluntary participation in project meetings likely introduced self-selection bias. To address this issue, in-person workshops included a booth at the Pembrokeshire Fair targeting a wide audience, and planned 1:1 farm walkover visits were modified to hold in-person workshops on host farms to increase participant numbers. In addition, farmers union county representatives from Anglesey, Pembrokeshire, and Monmouthshire, who represented broader community opinions, were present at the final summary workshop to assist in verification and revision of project results. Where possible, we have contextualized our results in terms of 232 responses to the

Welsh Government “Sustainable Farming and Our Land” consultation (O’Prey et al. 2021), and analysis of 286 Welsh beef/sheep farmers’ perspectives on climate change (Hyland et al. 2016) obtained through representative convenience sampling (Luschei et al. 2009).

2.2 Qualitative data analysis

Themes arising from meeting transcripts, post-visit interviews, and feedback forms were identified using a coding and categorisation process (Burnard 2004; Burnard et al. 2008). Five extrinsic codes were identified from the four project research questions and goal to collect feedback on project outputs: “barriers to implementation,” “decision making process,” “communication preferences,” “future of farming,” and “feedback on project outputs.” During the initial reading, two further intrinsic codes were identified: “working for the environment” and “aspects of sustainability.” Project data were then re-read and each element assigned one of the seven codes. Initial results were presented to participants for verification (November 2021). Notes from this meeting were read and coded using the structure applied to earlier data.

3. Results

Participants responded to the four project research questions, highlighting barriers to action, farmer decision making process for sustainable farming actions, communication preferences, and suggestions for the future of sustainable farming in Wales (Sections 3.1-3.4). In addition, emerging project themes including farmer perspective of “working for the environment” and identification of interlinked aspects of sustainability, which are presented following the four original research questions (Section 3.5).

3.1 Barriers to action

Participants identified key barriers to implementation of sustainable farming actions including time and cost, extreme weather events, and prevalence of tenanted land (Table 1). Participants felt constrained by time and money in farm business budgets, and lack of available long-term financial valuation for sustainable farming actions:

Although farmers are keen to do these works they are concerned about loss of land and lack of reward.

All this costs money. If we had more money, we could afford to do more things.

Lack of financial valuation presented barriers to incorporation of sustainable farming actions in farm budgets and obtaining funds on loan:

Just talking to the bank about silage pits, they say this will cost between £400-500k. There’s no money [to loan] because there’s no return on it.

Similarly, participants expressed concern that investment in sustainable farming actions would not be incorporated within farm assurance schemes, such as the Red Tractor, due to the lack of explicit financial valuation for associated provision of ecosystem services. For example, some participants in on-site meetings identified wet areas containing trees as “non-productive land” because ecosystem services provided by such areas did not form part of a long-term business plan and associated budget. In some cases, however participants identified cost as a positive factor contributing to the adoption of sustainable farming actions, with an increase in fertilizer cost (Autumn 2021; BBC Scotland 29 September 2021) seen as a positive factor contributing to adoption of on-farm composting and nutrient retention measures to reduce the need to purchase fertilizer from outside sources.

Participant-identified time and cost barriers echoed attitudes of Welsh farmers exhibiting positive attitudes towards productivism (49%, Hyland et al. 2016) and farmer attitudes towards sustainable farming actions internationally (Kik et al. 2001, Herzon and Mikk 2007, Holstead and Kenyon 2011). Time and cost were viewed as greater barriers for tenant farmers, with some participants expressing an

inability to implement significant alterations to rented land due to additional time needed for discussion and lack of long-term investment potential.

Weather patterns emerged as a significant additional barrier, both directly due to limited availability of dry, sunny weather conditions facilitating installation of sediment traps and ponds:

Can't put it in if too wet, can't do it if the weather won't allow

and indirectly due to occurrence of extreme weather events. Heavy rain in mid-May 2021 was brought up as an example of an extreme condition during which sediment loss would have occurred despite existing sustainable tillage practices:

We had 8-10 inches of rain in May. How can anyone manage that?

Participants expressed concern that occurrence of an extreme rainfall event at an inopportune time, for example just after tillage, could result in excess off-farm sediment and nutrient discharge despite implementation of sustainable farming actions. This raised concern that implementation would not reduce negative public perception or farmer time and financial burden.

Barrier	Impact
Long-term economic valuation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Justification of time and cost to implement action in business plan ○ Lack of access to bank loan without clear return on investment ○ Recognition of action by farm assurance schemes
Extreme weather events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Extreme flooding may overwhelm capacity or occur at inopportune time in tillage cycle, causing sediment and nutrient loss despite action taken ○ Fines and negative public perception linked to extreme event may persist despite action ○ Actions perceived as not working for intended purpose, even if effective at lower to moderate flow levels ○ Increased frequency of extreme rainfall and drought stresses farm business, reducing available time and money to implement actions
Tenanted land	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Reduced decision-making power and long-term investment ○ Associated with reduced social stability and economic prosperity

Table 1. Main barriers to implementation of sustainable farming actions identified by project participants, with identified practical impacts.

3.2 Decision-making process

In evaluating whether or not to implement a sustainable farming action, discussion with family, business partners, and other farmers emerged as a key decision-making step (*"a chat always comes first"*). Co-design of interventions and policy was viewed as a pathway to improve practical implementation and positive environmental outcomes. In some cases, participants felt restricted by policy, for example if reimbursement for an implemented sustainable farming action which would fit broad scheme goals was not possible due to an adapted intervention design.

Through discussion, participants attempted to balance needs of the land and farm business. Participants demonstrated a practical knowledge of the response of their land to storm conditions, and had considered placement and design of sustainable farming actions in order to make the best use of the available land while optimising the needs of the land and farm business. For example, the observed hydrologic response of land to storms was considered in farmer self-design of tree planting schemes (Figure 2), including identification of wet areas and locations with frequent overland flow. Trees were

described as occurring on the margins of farm fields and in wetter areas unsuitable for heavy grazing or arable crops, consistent with previous observations of positive farmer attitudes towards small-scale land sparing (Cusworth and Dodsworth 2021). Self-designed tree planting schemes in some cases were viewed as primarily generating ecosystem services (windbreak, capture of water, buffer for overland flow) and in others were considered as a long-term investment crop. Participants expressed positive views of trees as a wood products cash crop, windbreak for adjacent fields, and source of natural beauty. In some cases, participants felt restricted by policy, for example if reimbursement for an implemented sustainable farming action which would fit the broad goals of the scheme was not possible due to an adapted intervention design. In addition, the negative impact of the design of narrow fenced buffer strips, which resulted in invasive bramble growth and reduced biodiversity compared to an occasionally grazed or mowed strip, was brought up by participants:

Experience of streamside corridors have so far been disappointing as the lack of grazing means that it becomes inaccessible for everyone and everything and actually reduces biodiversity.

Participants expressed a willingness to engage in future two-way conversation and codesign of interventions and policy:

There's a lack of being able to design for your farm. It's too prescriptive.

Should be two way, designing toolkit and policy—Brilliant! Codesign policy is how it should be. That's why I'm doing it. I want my voice to be heard.

Participation in policy and intervention co-design was seen as a pathway to improve correspondence with practical implementation and positive environmental outcomes for sustainable farming actions.

3.3 Communication preferences

Discussion with family, business partners, and other farmers and reliance on the local farming community emerged as a key step in both decision making and knowledge transfer. Participants identified discussion with other farmers as a preferred communication pathway:

Community is very strong—this is very important in doing business in terms of knowledge transfer between farmers.

Discussion amongst other farmers in knowledge sharing groups is really important and I value this a lot. This is different to groups in which people want to sell you something or get you to do something. I value discussion amongst farmers.

Participants commented positively on the advantages of online meetings, especially in reducing fuel costs and connecting regions as far afield as the UK and Australia.

Zoom is a massive step forward. From NFU-engage with anybody in the world.

The limitations of “poor broadband [availability] and poor digital connection” were brought up as a disadvantage in some rural areas. Despite the benefits of online meetings, participants felt that in-person meetings had some additional benefits not possible online:

It's the way forward, but you miss that personal discussion after the meeting.

Recipients of 1:1 farm walkover visits highlighted the value of in-person, on-farm discussion in identifying practical application and design of sustainable farming actions. Following consultation with participants, project catchment-wide (Workshop 1, July 2021) and cross-catchment (Workshop 2, November 2021) meetings were held both to meet Covid-related restrictions (July 2021) and to address practical travel time and cost limitations in conducting a group workshop for all catchments (November 2021), which

were located across Wales (Figure 1). In addition to learning from community members, participants expressed appreciation for the two-way conversational nature aspects of project workshops and co-production of project outputs.

3.4 Suggestions for the future of sustainable farming in Wales

Despite identified barriers, participants were optimistic about the future of farming in Wales (*"We love the industry, that's why we do it"*) and expressed a willingness to be *"part of the solution"* (*"Lots could be done with a little bit of joined up thinking, really"*). Participants expressed a desire for future two-way conversations and co-design of agricultural policy and sustainable farming actions. In addition, participants suggested mechanisms for economic valuation of ecosystem services provided by sustainable farming actions, in the hope that this would reduce identified time and cost barriers to implementation and allow incorporation of investment in sustainable farming actions into farm business plans. Suggestions included payments for *"ecosystem services as a public good"* such as water filtration and potential flood alleviation, as well as management of *"highway runoff"* entering farm fields.

Participants expressed a strong desire for market-led solutions driven by positive public perception of sustainably produced food. Participants noted increasing interest in sustainable farming actions from retailers as positive public perceptions of sustainable farming trickled upwards to farmers:

Some farmers are already putting in cover crops for example as part of their retailer contract and rewarded for doing so. This will only increase as pressure builds on the climate change debate.

Farmer-owned cooperatives were advocated as a method to build pathways for knowledge transfer between cooperative members and *"support changes within that system,"* with sustainable farming action implementation ultimately driven by market success of the cooperative group. However, some participants raised caution over the cooperative model as a pathway to long-term success (*"There's a big history of failures. They need to be run well"*). A combination of strategies with an emphasis on market-led solutions was advocated as a practical way forward.

Participants in Pembrokeshire and Anglesey emphasized the cultural and practical importance of the Welsh Language, including that county farmers union meetings were usually conducted in Welsh.

3.5 Emerging project themes

Participants demonstrated a shared feeling of pride in farmers' traditional role as *"custodians of the land."* Hedgerow trimming and coppicing of tree stands were highlighted as examples of traditional environmental guardianship:

I want others to understand that we are working for the environment.

Who would trim the hedgerows if the farmers didn't do it? What would the land look like? It's a beautiful landscape.

We all want clean water and love the environment, but us farmers can't produce for what it costs.

Participants felt *"under appreciated, misunderstood, undervalued"* by the perceived depiction of farmers as uncaring or polluters. In contrast, participants felt that existing barriers prevented farmers from wider implementation of sustainable farming actions.

In addition, participants built on the term *"sustainable farming"* to identify multiple aspects of sustainability including environmental, economic, social, and cultural sustainability (Figure 2, solid black circles) and the relationship between these aspects, depicted by lines in Figure 2. Social, cultural and economic sustainability were identified as interlinked components necessary to achieve environmental sustainability:

There are different types or components to sustainability: social, economic, environmental

There's a cultural aspect, we're Welsh speaking areas; rural, farming communities are guardians of the Welsh Language, so there's a cultural aspect of sustainability around that as well

Participants identified economic sustainability as a necessary condition for social and environmental sustainability. Sustainability was seen as “*embedded in stability*,” and the four identified aspects were described as “*intertwined in a lot of ways*.” Economic success was seen as contributing to business longevity and farm ownership, with associated positive contributions to the welfare of the local community, including the local economy and long-term development of community social links. Participants associated social stability with cultural stability and Welsh Language longevity, as spoken Welsh could continue to be passed down to the next generation.

News of the purchase of farmland in Carmarthenshire, Wales, as part of a tree planting scheme for carbon capture by the London-based investment company Foresight Group (Summer 2021; Garside and Wyn 2021) was brought up in multiple meetings as an example of an effort to achieve environmental sustainability to the detriment of local social, cultural and economic sustainability. Purchase of farmland for tree planting by an outside group was seen as reducing locally available farmland and housing, while generating value primarily outside the local community. In addition, participants expressed concern about the net carbon offset benefit of tree planting, which in part depended on the tree end use. Concern for the “*wider benefit*” extended to a range of sustainable farming actions, with participants advocating a strong desire for involvement that made a positive practical contribution to environmental health and climate change.

Figure 2. Definitions and spatial relationship (black lines) between environmental, economic, social, and cultural aspects of sustainability identified by project participants (black solid circles). The centrality and interdependence of economic and environmental sustainability was emphasized during verification by participants in Workshop 2.

4. Discussion

4.1 Interlinked aspects of sustainability

The farmer-identified framework of interrelated economic, environmental, social, and cultural aspects of sustainability (Figure 2) resembles Bourdieu social theory, in which economic, social, and cultural capital are required to generate symbolic capital (Bourdieu 1986; Hilgers and Mangez 2015; Cudsworth and Dodsworth 2021). To achieve a successful environmental outcome, sufficient support for interlinked economic, social, and cultural aspects was required. For example, economic success was seen as contributing to business longevity and farm ownership, with associated positive contributions to community welfare, including the local economy and social links. Participants associated social stability with cultural stability and Welsh Language longevity, transferred through intergenerational family networks. Further, economic sustainability was described as both the incorporation of sustainable farming actions into long-term business plans to realise return on initial investment, and long-term economic confidence that the farm business would be profitable and survive to be passed down to the next generation.

In addition to identifying interlinkages between economic, social and cultural aspects and positive environmental outcomes, participants viewed positive environmental contributions as linked to broader identity and outcomes, taking pride in their longstanding caretaking role as “*guardians of the countryside*” and “*working for the environment.*” For example, hedgerow trimming and coppicing were highlighted as examples of traditional environmental guardianship, echoing motivations expressed by 51% of respondent farmers exhibiting high levels of environmental responsibility (Hyland et al. 2016). However, due to the small sample size and self-selection bias, project participant views were likely more representative of farmers with higher levels of knowledge and engagement with sustainable farming actions rather than the community as a whole. An investigation of English farmers also observed generally positive attitudes towards delivery of diverse farming objectives including ecosystem services and food production, suggesting that widespread recognition of the expanding economic market for farmer-provided services had reduced previous negative associations with untidiness and non-productivity (Burton et al. 2008; Cudsworth and Dodsworth 2021).

4.2 Perceptions of tree planting

Design of tree-planting schemes was highlighted as an example of the participant-generated framework (Figure 2), with a successful environmental outcome requiring consideration of interlinked economic, social and cultural aspects over the long term. Participants favoured support of pre-existing trees and self-design of tree planting that complemented their existing livelihood (Figure 3), with participants expressing positive attitudes towards existing countryside trees and farmers’ role in caring for historic tree stands through coppicing and hedgerow maintenance. Existing countryside trees and farmer self-designed tree planting schemes were described as occurring on the margins of farm fields and in wetter areas unsuitable for heavy grazing or arable crops. Positive participant attitudes towards tree planting in areas generally viewed as unsuitable for other agricultural use is consistent with previous observations of farmer preference for “*land sparing,*” in which part of a field, often marginal land, is set aside for generation of ecosystem services (Cudsworth and Dodsworth 2021).

Although participants expressed positive attitudes towards land sparing at small spatial scales, strong negative viewpoints were expressed for land sparing at the larger whole-farm scale (Figure 3), linked to the recent purchase of Carmarthenshire farmland for use as tree plantations for carbon offsetting by the London-based Foresight Group (Garside and Wyn 2021). Alteration of ownership and management of farmland at this scale was linked to loss of local housing and livelihoods, due to the whole farm scale of the purchase of land by an outside group, instead of individual farmers, and expected low maintenance requirement of planned projects and associated low expectations for local employment. In this type of scheme design, whole-farm scale land purchase was seen as negatively affecting the local economy, as any profit would be realised by the outside landowner, and negatively impacting local social and cultural ties, due to reduced availability of local housing and farmland, reducing confidence that young people would be able to remain in the local community. Participants worried that due to the strong market for carbon credits, such purchases could become commonplace, eliminating rural farming communities.

Participant concerns echoed recent results examining the complexities of tree planting design internationally (Fleischman et al. 2020; Coleman et al. 2021). An analysis of 50 years' investment in Indian tree planting schemes (Coleman et al. 2021) revealed no net increase in canopy cover. Because targeted areas were already under use as farmland, most planting occurred in marginal areas with tree cover already present. In response to concerns generated by analysis of existing tree-planting schemes, development of people-centred nature-based solutions that support local social, economic and political needs has been advocated (Fleischman et al. 2020).

Figure 3. Positive and negative attributes of tree planting identified by project participants.

4.3 Pathways forward in Wales for implementation of sustainable farming actions

Participants expressed positive views of sustainable farming actions but were limited from further implementation by time and cost barriers, underscoring the complex physical and social nature of implementing nature-based solutions for natural flood management and sustainable farming (Wingfield et al. 2021) and advantages of incorporating “people-centred” aspects into design of nature-based solutions (Fleischman et al. 2020). The participant-generated framework of interlinked support for economic, social and cultural aspects in order to achieve successful environmental outcomes (Figure 2) can be used as a framework to examine farmer barriers to action and suggested pathways forward in Wales.

Participant-identified economic barriers of time and cost, as well as the central link between economic and environmental sustainability, echoed attitudes of farmers and value chain participants in a study of soil management in the Netherlands, where they prioritized economics and income as key criteria for sustainable soil management (Kik et al. 2021). Scottish farmers expressed major concerns about the effect of natural flood management measures on business viability, with 58% of 193 survey respondents indicating that more funding would encourage them to implement such measures (Holstead and Kenyon 2011). Similarly, Estonian farmers highlighted their concern for environmentally beneficial land management measures that affected farm productivity, with farmers who viewed environmental issues as more important being more likely to implement such measures (Herzon and Mikk 2007). To reduce economic barriers, participants emphasized market-led methods but suggested a combination of mechanisms including valuation of practices that increase ecosystem services in retailer contracts, farm

cooperative business models, government subsidy programs, and development of explicit financial valuation for ecosystem services linked to sustainable farming actions, enabling inclusion in lending models and farm assurance schemes. Similarly, responses to recent consultation advocated the positive benefits of a mix of market and government support in both provision of public goods and food production, with government subsidy acting as a protection from market fluctuations (Welsh Government 2020b; O'Prey et al. 2021). While respondents to a Welsh Government consultation on agroecological policy (O'Prey et al. 2021) expressed a generally positive attitude towards sustainable farming actions, respondents also raised the need for regulatory mechanisms to enforce compliance with environmental regulations including fines and criminal prosecution for serious offences. A proportional regulatory scheme was advocated to create a non-confrontational regulatory environment where possible (O'Prey et al. 2021).

Participant preferences for communication pathways that support local social and cultural links, such as community discussion and knowledge transfer among farmers, were consistent with positive outcomes of farmer-to-farmer training models (Kansaga et al. 2021). A targeted one-to-one advice model was recently expanded in England to cover all catchments as part of increased investment (£30M/annum) for the Catchment Sensitive Farming programme (Defra Press Office, 2 August 2021). Participants in this study who elected to receive an on-farm walkover visit felt that in-person, on-farm discussion provided practical value in identifying options for implementation of sustainable farming actions. In a recent public consultation period ("Agriculture (Wales) White Paper," Welsh Government 2020a) respondents emphasized the importance provision of farm advisory services, such as Farming Connect, and clear communication of targeted advice and guidance in improving farmer knowledge and implementation of new regulations, as well as the necessity of considering overall cost and practicality of advice provision (O'Prey et al. 2021). Efforts to develop and refine digital tools to initially identify and target farm advice, such as the EU Horizon 2020 FAIRshare project (<https://www.h2020fairshare.eu/news-and-events/communication-materials/>) could assist in broadening targeted advice provision while maintaining or reducing overall costs. In addition to expressing a preference for community discussion and farmer-to-farmer knowledge transfer, project participants in Pembrokeshire and Anglesey emphasized the cultural and practical importance of the Welsh Language, including that county farm union meetings were usually conducted in Welsh, suggesting that Welsh-speaking advisors may be of particular interest in these and other areas where Welsh is commonly used. Use of spoken Welsh was also highlighted in consultation response (O'Prey et al. 2021), suggesting that Welsh-speaking advisors may be beneficial.

4. Conclusion

In this study, Welsh farmer perspectives on sustainable farming actions including barriers to implementation, decision-making processes, communication preferences, and suggestions for the future of sustainable farming were examined. Key barriers included time and cost to implement sustainable farming actions, availability of long-term financial valuation for ecosystem services, occurrence of extreme weather events, and presence of tenanted land (Table 1). Farmer to farmer knowledge transfer and decision making through discussion with family, business partners, and other farmers aided participants in balancing perceived land hydrological needs with farm business requirements. Reflecting this community-based framework, participants highlighted interlinkage between environmental sustainability and broader aspects of social, economic, and cultural sustainability (Figure 2). Design of tree planting schemes was discussed as an example, with positive attitudes expressed toward countryside trees in wetter areas or on the margins of fields, but concerns were raised towards farm-scale land sparing that reduced local housing and farmland availability (Figure 3). This perspective unites environmental and productivity oriented motivations identified in a prior survey of Welsh beef and sheep farmer attitudes to climate change (Hyland et al. 2016). In line with participant views of interlinked environmental, economic, social, and cultural components, initiatives targeting economic barriers while supporting existing social and cultural links were seen as pathways forward for implementation of sustainable farming actions, supporting farmer-led innovation and knowledge transfer pathways. Existing initiatives targeting the whole community such as Farming Connect (Welsh Government 2023) and the

Well-being of Future Generations (Wales) Act 2015 could serve as a basis for future support, alongside use of a bilingual in-person farm advisor role with targeted online tools.

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Data Availability Statement

The datasets generated during and/or analysed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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